

reaction to two potential fungicides, methyl benzimidazole carbamate (MBC) and methoxyethyl mercury chloride (MEMC). MBC was more effective on both isolates.

No appreciable differences in

pathogenicity could be found between the isolates on soybean (highly susceptible to both), *Imperata cylindrica*, *Saccharum spontaneum*, and water hyacinth (less susceptible to both). But on *Colocasia antiquorum*, R did not

incite infection and B was virulent. Pusa 2-21 was highly susceptible to both isolates, but only B was virulent on IR8, IET3267, and RP4-41. It was concluded that the isolates constituted distinct strains. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

New record of a rice leaf miner, *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer (Diptera: Agromyzidae), in the Philippines

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Observations on rice seedlings in Iloilo, Pangasinan, and Laguna provinces, Philippines, in 1977 and 1978 revealed the presence of an unknown leaf miner. The same leaf miner attacked both transplanted and direct-seeded rice.

The mines (10–42 mm long, and 1–4 mm wide) run parallel to the leaf

blade and usually occur at the apices. Each dissected leaf mine had a single white larva 0.80 to 2.00 mm long. The larva pupated within the mine, protected by the upper and lower epidermis of the leaf. The puparium, 1.35 mm long and 0.65 mm wide, appears mat, and each segment boundary is marked by 4 or 5 rows of irregularly placed spines. The puparium is generally glued firmly within the mine. Adult flies that emerged from infested leaves bearing pupae were identified as *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer by Dr. M. Sasakawa of Kyoto Prefectural University, Japan. The adults can be distinguished from related species by the bluntly angulate third antennal segment, mat mesonotum, grayish orbits, black lateral sides of thorax, largely colorless $M_1 + 2$ and $M_3 + 4$, and the squamae and fringe are conspicuously silvery white.

P. asiatica is widely distributed in Asia but this is the first account of its being a rice pest in the Philippines. Another host, *Cynodon dactylon*, was reported in Singapore in 1961.

Pseudonapomyza atra has been mentioned as a leaf miner on rice in India and Taiwan, but according to taxonomists it is distributed in the temperate regions of North America and Europe. Therefore, the early records of *P. atra* in Asia probably referred to *P. asiatica*. ■

Spiders check planthopper population

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Spiders of different families have been reported to prey on the brown planthopper (BPH). Large numbers of spiders (av 2/hill) are seen on the rice crop, especially during later growth stages, near Kuttanadu, Kerala, where the BPH has become endemic. During a severe BPH incidence in the main punja season (Oct–Feb) field plots were treated with six insecticides. Six days after treatment, the populations of both BPH and spiders were lower than those in the untreated plots. Fifteen days after treatment the populations increased and the effect of insecticide treatment was not significant. During the next crop season (Apr–Sep), when insecticide application was negligible, the spider populations were high and the BPH population low.

These observations suggest that spiders are potential natural enemies of the BPH and that they can keep its population well below the economic threshold.

Photo 1. Rice leaves with damage (mines) and pupae of *P. asiatica*.

Photo 2. Adult fly of *P. asiatica*.

Based on field cage trials, seven spider species were found to be efficient predators: *Lucosa* sp., *Pholcys* sp., *Marpissa mandali* Tikader, *Tetragnatha* sp., *Linyphia* sp., *Oxyopes sakuntalae* Tikader, and *Argiope undulata* Thorell. Their feeding potential is being investigated. ■

Natural biological suppression agents of rice pests in the eastern plains of Colombia

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The ecology of paddy rice pests was investigated during three successive growing semesters in 1977-78 at the La Libertad experiment station, Villavicencio, Meta. Control measures were not necessary because each potential economic pest was suppressed by natural enemies.

Trichogramma sp. or *Telenomus* sp. parasitized >95% of the eggs of the sugarcane stem borer *Diatraea saccharalis* F. The larval parasitoid *Agathis stigmaterus* Cresson was active in the plots each season. Borer damage never exceeded 3%, the level along borders.

During each crop unidentified epizootics of entomopathogens suppressed populations of leafhopper, mainly *Hortensia similis* (Walker) and *Draeculacephala clypeata* Osborn, by 70 to 95% (field estimate). Those species never caused an economic level of damage. The defoliators *Spodoptera* spp. and *Panoquina* spp. were effectively suppressed by fungal epizootics of *Paecilomyces tenuipes* (Peck) Samson (identified by R. A. Humber, Boyce Thompson Institute, Ithaca, N.Y., USA). Estimates of successful field infection rates ranged from 95 to 99% during each crop, which apparently was sufficient to maintain the species at lower than economic levels. Various tachnids parasitized the Pentatomid species. The rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus oryzophilus* Kuschel (considered the Legion's major rice pest) was absent from the experimental plots.

No pest control measures were necessary because of the natural suppression complexes in the fields during the three rice crops.

Noe Arias, Practico, ICA, La Libertad, Villavicencio, collected *Diatraea* eggs and did most of the laboratory parasite counts. ■

Field efficacy of a fungus, a bacterium, and organic insecticides against rice pests

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The successful control of vegetable pests with low doses of organic insecticides and entomogenous organisms has encouraged the testing of such

combinations against rice insect pests.

A field trial was established to determine the performance of white halo fungus (*Cephalosporium lecanii* Zimm.), a bacterium (*Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *alesti* Berliner Dipel), and of the two with dichlorvos or phosalone.

Phosalone reduced rice borer incidence slightly. Neither the fungus nor the bacterium reduced incidence of whorl maggot, stem borer, or leaf folder.

Effect of combinations of insect pathogens and insecticides on the incidence of rice insect pests. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Damage ^a (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	Whorl maggot	Stem borer	Leaf roller	
Fungus (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml)	12.6 d	11.9 b	0.6 c	2.9
Fungus + phosalone (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml) (1.42 ml/liter)	11.6 c	13.3 c	0.3 ab	3.1
Fungus + dichlorvos (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml) (2 ml/liter)	10.9 b	11.7 b	0.4 bc	3.2
Dipel (5.5 g/liter)	11.6 c	11.3 b	0.5 bc	3.2
Dipel + phosalone (2.75 g/liter) (1.42 ml/liter)	13.1 d	11.6 b	1.4 e	3.2
Dipel + dichlorvos (2.75 g/liter) (2 ml/liter)	11.9 c	12.4 b	0.2 ab	2.9
Phosalone (2.85 ml/liter)	10.3 a	8.6 a	0.5 c	3.3
Dichlorvos (4 ml/liter)	11.7 c	9.6 a	0.1 a	3.4
Phosalone + dichlorvos (1.42 ml/liter) (2 ml/liter)	11.4 bc	11.6 b	0.2 ab	3.2
Untreated control	11.9 d	12.4 c	0.4 d	2.3
Significance	*	*	*	n.s.
CD at 5% level	0.5	1.2	0.25	

^a Mean values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

Ovicidal and larvicidal activity of some insecticides on leaf folder

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Four insecticides — methyl parathion, triazophos, methomyl, and carbofuran — at 0.04% concentration were tested on eggs and freshly hatched larvae of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. Two-day-old eggs of leaf folder from the greenhouse culture were dipped in the prepared insecticidal solutions for

1 minute. The control was eggs dipped in water. Both treated and untreated eggs were placed in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and were observed daily. Three days after the treatment, the control eggs hatched. Most treated eggs did not hatch although embryonic development was completed (see table). Some eggs treated with methomyl hatched but the larvae were weak and died within minutes. In an earlier study ovicidal activity of carbofuran and triazophos against the